

ADAPTATION OF THE BODY OF DENTIST STUDENTS TO PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES**Aslonov Javlon Farmonovich**

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It is well known that physical activity has a direct impact on the functional state of the human body. During physical exercise, the body needs to optimize itself to a new state. The definition of optimization to physical activity is that the body not only adapts to the size of the weight lifted, high or slow speed, but also adapts to changes in functions, biochemical processes and the humoral reactions they cause.

In addition, the psychological and emotional background of competitive activity changes.

A characteristic feature of adaptive functional systems is their flexibility and lability to achieve the same results in various conditions of the external and internal environment.

The functions of these systems are performed with maximum conservation of human resources. The relevance of studying the adaptation of the body to physical activity is beyond doubt, since physical education and sports are becoming the norm of life and an indispensable attribute of personal success for many citizens of our country. The purpose of this work was to study the processes of adaptation of the body to physical activity.

Under the influence of properly organized physical exercises, the plastic process is enhanced, which leads to accelerated formation of bone tissue during human growth. This process is most clearly manifested in childhood. In addition, moderate physical activity lasting 1.5-2.0 hours can cause an increase in the level of growth hormone in the blood by 3 times. And the higher the level of somatotropin, the more intense the growth of a person.

It is noted that systematic physical activity has a positive effect on the functional state of the respiratory system.

The strength and endurance of the respiratory muscles increases, the size of the lungs and the depth of breathing increase with a simultaneous decrease in the frequency of respiratory movements, which significantly improves the processes of gas exchange in the lungs and more fully meets the body's need for oxygen. In addition, it is noted that sports training increases the body's resistance to low temperatures, preventing the development of diseases of the respiratory system. Physiological changes in the respiratory system also manifest themselves in the form of an increase in the oxygen utilization coefficient and an increase in the ability of the respiratory center to maintain excitation at the maximum level for a long time. The oxygen capacity of the blood and the ability of skeletal muscles to use oxygen from the blood increase, due to which conditions are created for reducing pulmonary ventilation, both at rest and during physical exertion. Regular physical exercise contributes to an increase in the number of alveoli by 15-20%, which creates a significant anatomical and functional reserve of breathing. Some authors note that cyclic physical exercise leads to an increase in the volume-velocity indicators of the respiratory system. Thus, in the studies of N.G. Varlamova, it was found that people involved in cross-country skiing have higher airway patency in different areas than people who do not engage in sports. The cardiovascular system plays a leading role in ensuring the body's adaptation to physical activity, thereby limiting the development of the body's adaptive response. Systematic physical exercise promotes intensive development of the heart and improves its function. Many morphological rearrangements occur in the myocardium, that is, the synthesis of contractile protein increases, the number of mitochondria increases and the concentration of myoglobin in the capillary network increases in proportion to the increase in heart mass.

All this leads to moderate hypertrophy of the myocardium and an increase in its cavity, so cardiac output increases and the pulse rate decreases.

These morphological and functional rearrangements provide cardiac economy and adapt the cardiovascular system to various muscle loads. It is common for people who exercise regularly to experience sinus bradycardia at rest, which is characterized by a low heart rate. Most often, a slowdown in the heart rate occurs in people who regularly engage in cyclic exercises to develop endurance. A decrease in heart rate in an athlete is a manifestation of the influence of the vagus nerve on the sinus node and is considered a more efficient and economical circulatory system. This is due to the fact that filling in the ventricles is created during prolonged diastole and the metabolic process of the myocardium is completely restored after the previous contraction. One of the main manifestations as a result of a decrease in heart rate at rest is considered to be a decrease in myocardial oxygen demand. At the initial stage of training, the stroke volume of blood tends to increase its values, and as the sports experience increases, its values stabilize, which contributes to a decrease in the minute volume of blood at rest. In addition to the positive effect on the health of the person involved, physical activity can have a negative effect on the functional state and cause various diseases and injuries. This occurs as a result of the discrepancy between the load performed and the functional capabilities of the body.

Excessive load can cause inhibition of plastic processes and delay in growth and development of the body. Intensive physical activity for a long time, especially in combination with unfavorable environmental conditions, can cause and maintain inflammatory changes in the respiratory tract. Thus, I.M Vuljanko, D. Plavec note that people engaged in open space environments are exposed to cold air, which can contribute to an increased risk of dysfunction of the respiratory system. Adaptation to physical activity is manifested in the form of changes in the functional state of the human body. Basically, these manifestations are positive, however, if the load does not match the functional capabilities, they can have a negative impact on the functional state and cause various diseases and injuries.

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